

Additional File 5: List of parameters of the mathematical models A and B, respectively.

Symbol	Definition	Unit	Value
MODEL A			
d	Differentiation rate from C ₋ to C ₊	[1/h]	estimated
r ₁	Maximum shedding rate for non-infected CD163 positive cells, i.e. transition rate from C ₊ to C ₋ .	[1/h]	estimated
f _r	Half saturation concentration of compound P for receptor shedding	[1]	estimated
m ₋ , m ₊ , m _{+/-}	Mortality rates for non-infected C ₋ , C ₊ and C _{+/-} cells, respectively	[1/h]	estimated
c ₁ , c ₂	Proportion of C ₋ and C ₊ cells, respectively, at start of incubation (time = 0)	[1]	estimated
b _{max}	Maximum infection rate	[1/h]	estimated
f _b	Half saturation concentration of compound Q for infection	[1]	estimated
p _P , p _Q	Production rate of compounds P and Q, respectively	[1/h]	0.5*
s _P , s _Q	Decay rates of compounds P and Q, respectively	[1/h]	0.5*
r ₂	Maximum shedding rate for infected CD163 positive cells, i.e. transition rate from C* ₊ to C* _{+/-} .	[1/h]	estimated
a ₊ , a ₋	Mortality rates for infected C* ₊ and C* _{+/-} cells, respectively	[1/h]	estimated
MODEL B			
δ ₁	Differentiation rate from C-M ₋ to C+M ₋	[1/h]	estimated
δ ₂	Differentiation rate from C-M ₊ to C+M ₊	[1/h]	estimated
σ _{1,max}	Max. (de) activation rate between C-M ₋ and C-M ₊	[1/h]	estimated
σ _{2,max}	Max. (de) activation rate between C+M ₋ and C+M ₊	[1/h]	estimated

ε	Constant determining how gradual the susceptibility state switches as F approaches F_T	[1]	0.1*
F_T	Threshold value for compound F	[1]	estimated
γ	Production rate for compound F	[1/h]	0.5*
ω	Decay rate for compound F	[1/h]	0.5*
$\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4$	Mortality rates for non-infected C-M-, C+M-, C-M+ and C+M+ cells, respectively	[1/h]	estimated
$\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$	Proportion of C-M-, C+M- and C-M+ cells, respectively, at start of incubation (t=0)	[1]	estimated
β_1	Infection rate for C-M+ cells, i.e. transition rate from C-M+ to C-*M+*	[1/h]	estimated
β_2	Infection rate for C+M+ cells, i.e. transition rate from C+M+ to C+*M+*	[1/h]	estimated
α_3, α_4	Mortality rates for infected C-*M+* and C+*M+* cells, respectively	[1/h]	estimated

Identifiability analysis revealed poor identifiability of model parameters controlling the density dependent effects of autocrine substances (i.e. quantities P,Q in model A and F in model B) and confounding between the shedding and infection rates (f, Q_b in model A) and switching rates (F_T in model B) with the respective production rates (parameters p_P, p_Q in model A, and γ in model B) and decay rates (parameters s_P, s_Q in model A and ω in model B) of these compounds. To remedy this issue, we fixed all production and decay rates of these compounds to the arbitrary constant value of 0.5 and estimated the remaining parameters through model fitting. For similar reasons, the constant ε in model B was set to the arbitrary value of 0.1.